

Green Marketing and Benefits to Business

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Abstract

Nowadays, businesses are aware that they cannot carry on without being aware of environmental problems. Businesses have to take environmental aspects of all activities in their business strategies and long-term plans.

Those environmental activities and green marketing are started to be taken into consideration by so many businesses. In this study, green marketing is examined. Today, despite taking part among scarce resources, unfortunately, necessary importance is not given to the environment. A Limited number of Businesses show awareness on that issue.

Keywords: Environment, business, green marketing.

Introduction

It is observed that the concept of environment and viewpoints about the environment- in parallel with results of social, economic, political developments and environmental problems- considerably undergo a change in recent years. Chimney gasses, toxic waste, and other waste which occur as the result of industrialization which has started in England with the industrial revolution and continued with advancing in other Western countries cause serious environmental problems. While ambitious and unrestrained production desire cause waste of sources, fabrication waste, and consumption waste have started to pollute atmosphere, seas, rivers and lands internationally. In the beginning of 21st century, this pollution prompted to countries for searching internationally binding solutions about how the world is going to be cleaned. With the aim of being protected by environmental threats of rapid development and unrestrainedly increasing trade, international environmental organizations have started to come up in the second half of the 19th century. Nowadays, businesses in any field have understood that they cannot carry on without being sensitive toward environmental problems.

Objectives

- To Evaluate the existing performance of the business in large scaled.
- To Promising the measurement of observation, examination, reporting and recovery in the performance.

- To Developing achievable environmental policies with open target and implementation schedule.
- To Following the development of green agenda.

Green Marketing Concept

Green marketing concept which has entered in the 1980s marketing literature is used synonymously with ecologic, environmentalist or environmental marketing, sustained marketing concepts (Ay and Elevate, 2005). Green Marketing as discussed and identified in “ecologic marketing” seminar prepared by American Marketing Association in 1975 for the first time. According to this identification, ecologic marketing is studies which are related marketing activities ‘positive and negative effects of environmental pollution, energy consumption and other sources consumption

History of Green Marketing

In the history of green marketing, ecologic marketing, environmentalist marketing, green marketing and sustained marketing concepts should be discussed altogether. Ecologic marketing is used in the strict sense to define some environmental problems such as pollution, energy sources extinction and marketing activities to prevent these ones with the existing technology. In environmentalist and green marketing concepts, there is an administrative perspective which involves broader product category and philosophy (Ay and Ecevit, 2005)

First Stage: Ecologic Marketing

Origin of the ecologic marketing dates to social and environmental concerns which occur at the beginning of the 60s and 70s. Thoughts of that period foresee that no controllable growth will waste natural resources and system that we need and they focus on the earth on which we live will have an end.

Second Stage: Environmentalist Marketing

The second stage of green marketing has occurred towards to end of the 1980s. This stage is the period that today’ smolder green marketing principals have occurred and developed. A range of events and discoveries attract the attention of the defenselessness of the people and nature.

Bhopal disaster named as the worst chemical disaster in the world in 1984, Chernobyl catastrophe in 1986, environmental pollution caused by Exxon-Valdes tanker in 1989 and discovered ozone layer depletion in 1995 are the events that start the change are the events that start the change. Conducted studies in the 90s in the USA reveal that the large part of the consumers are ready for paying to greener products

Green Marketing Implementations in the World

Dirty environment as the result of developing technology, increasing overpopulation and changing consumptions habits has started to threatened human health and natural environment. The countries which realize this situation and decide to take measures have signed the Kyoto Protocol. Kyoto Protocol is the most concrete and the only international environmental protocol which is about global warming and climate change. With that protocol, it is aimed to balance greenhouse gasses density in the level of safety for the climate. It is also planned to be signed by the countries which have signatures in United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (unfccc) under the control of United Nations.

Green Marketing and Businesses

The 1990s is named as “ World’s ten years” and the most important topic is seen as conservation of the natural environment. Businesses have returned to this issue with green marketing. Thus, the nature saving products development, reusable and recyclable packing, better pollution control and operations which will provide bettered efficiency are included in green marketing. Environmentalist marketing (green marketing) should be seen as a part of the whole environmental management and this realization is so important

Businesses can turn the environmental problems into opportunities. For example; some natural energy sources such as energy saving in heating and lighting, low-cost wind farms and hydroelectric projects are used by businesses. Also, businesses see hundreds of green products (eco-friendly product) as an opportunity.

Businesses that follow the green marketing agenda should fulfill some aspects such as developing presentations for protecting energy and other resources, creating advertisements and advertising messages reflecting businesses, Environmental contributions, price selection which is going to balance consumer’s cost sensibility with the higher one which they accept for ecologist product, decreasing the materials usage which cause environmental pollution and saving resources on disposal of products

Green Marketing Stages

Green marketing consists of four stages. Respectively these stages are green targeting, developing green strategies, environmental orientation and considering the business socially responsible (Keleş, 2007).

Green Targeting

In this stage, while green products are produced for the green consumers, business continues to product not-green products as well. For example, in the automobile industry, while hybrid, electronic cars and the ones which work with alternative technology are studied in Ar-Ge department, in the environmentalists’ part, sports car seen as the reason for noise and air pollution are produced, too.

Developing Green Strategies

Production of green and not-green products is continued. In this stage, the business tries to develop environmental strategies and determine its’ environment policies. In this stage, business takes some Ecologist measures such as less waste generation and increasing the energy efficiency.

Environmental Orientation

Producing just green products after stop the not-green products production. Hence, Consumers’ not-green products demands are not important.

Considering the Business Socially Responsible

Being or getting green is not enough. The business achieves social Responsibility awareness in every sense

Green Marketing and Traditional Marketing

To be able to understand primary commodities of green markets, elements of traditional markets should be. Traditional marketing not only specifies the number of the green consumers but also it analyzes present and future Opportunities of the market they also try to reach to consumers who resistive To the product or do not realize it with the help of new communication implementations.

Differences between Traditional and Green Marketing are Shown

Table 1 Differences between Traditional and Green Marketing (Keleş, 2007)

Criteria	Traditional Marketing	Green marketing
Sides that need bartering	Fire and consumers	Firm, consumer and environment
Target	Customer Satisfaction, firm target's Satisfaction	Customer Satisfaction, firm targets' satisfaction and minimizing caused ecologic effect
Business responsibility	Economic responsibility	Social responsibility

Criticisms for Green Marketing

Johri and Sahasakmontri (1998) have stated that environmentalist concerns have decreased because of the consumer's view of "green hypocrisy" in eng land. also, firms see the environmentalism as a short-term issue rather than as a long-term matter. in eng land, it is claimed that body shop continued apart from their consumers' mood adaptation and so its performance has decreased. One of the underlying reasons for the failures of environmentalist products is that making wrong decisions about the product's benefit when it is compared with real need. In the business world, it is really hard to be able to determine the one which pollutes and the one which protects the environment. For example; a firm may have ecologist fame as well as abusing human rights because of troubles in working conditions.

Consumers' who have worried about green issue buy green products, however, as a contingency effect, these buying behaviors haven't decreased the market share of green products. This situation is detected by so many literature studies. It is determined some problems such as consumer's cynicism, the complexity of the green product, green persist emceed generally trust problem about green marketing.

It is possible to associate marketing mix with consumers', not shopping behaviors that are the result of their green Concern's. According to this (Shamdasani and diğ., 1993):

- Green alternatives are not better in terms of their functions,
- Green alternatives are so expensive,
- Labels, according to claim that they protect the environment are not persuasive,
- Finding green alternatives is really hard.

Conclusion

Today, despite taking part among scarce resources, unfortunately, necessary importance is not given to the environment. A Limited number of businesses show awareness on that issue. Although problems about the environment date back, studies about this issue still are not enough. In the same way, studies about "Green Marketing" which has come to rise recently are not enough as well.

Consequently, within the scope of rapidly-developing technology and changing world, businesses have important responsibilities about protecting the environment and producing eco-friendly green products. The business which fulfills that duty is going to be one that can survive in the future.

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